

An adjustable cleft based on an 8-sulfonamide-2-naphthoic acid with oxyanion hole geometry

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Dedicated to Prof. François Diederich. So grateful to be part of the Diederich chemistry family: his contagious enthusiasm and inspiration always will guide us.

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Abstract: Cleft type receptors showing the oxyanion hole motif have been prepared in a straightforward synthesis starting from the commercial 3,7-dihydroxy-2-naphthoic acid. The double H-bond donor pattern is achieved by the introduction of a sulfonamide group in the C-8 position of naphthalene and a carboxamide at the C-2 position. This cleft, whose geometry resembles that of an oxyanion hole, is able to adjust to different guests, as shown by the analysis of the X-ray crystal structures of associates with methanol or acetic acid. Combination of hydrogen bonds and charge-transfer interactions led to further stabilization of the complexes, in which the electron-rich aromatic ring of the receptor was close in space to the electron-deficient dinitroaromatic guests. Modelling studies and bidimensional NMR experiments have been carried out to provide additional information.

The oxyanion hole is a well-established feature in enzyme catalysis.^[1] Two strong linear H-bonds stabilize the transition state because the charged carbonyl oxygen undergoes stronger H-bonds than the neutral ground state, reducing therefore the transition state energy. In this sense, rigid, broad oxyanion holes may not be ideal for catalysis, since stronger H-bonds mean also shorter distances between H-bond donors and acceptors;^[2] thus, an adjustable oxyanion hole would be better to increase the energy difference between ground and transition states. Conventional oxyanion hole mimics, as the classic isophthalic acid derivatives used extensively by Hamilton^[3] or pyridine 2,6-dicarboxylic acid derivatives used by Hunter,^[4] showed distances

around 5 Å between the NHs, which is well suited for ground state association, as judged for the many published receptors.^[5] To get a narrow oxyanion hole-like cleft, an amide and a sulfonamide groups have been placed over a naphthalene skeleton. Carboxamides and sulfonamides have very different geometries as H-bond donors; the need for conjugation of the nitrogen non-bonding electron pair with the sulfur orbitals in sulfonamides, directs the H-bond essentially in a nearly perpendicular direction to the carboxamide, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Different geometries between NH donors in the naphthalene skeleton: bis-carboxamide cleft (left) and sulfonamide-carboxamide cleft (right).

Placing the sulfonamide in the C-8 position on a 2-naphthoic acid amide skeleton, provides an ideal oxyanion hole with distances which are adaptable as a function of the C-S torsion, and can be as short as 4.7 Å. Also, the presence of the H-1 in the cleft may provide an additional H-bond (CH \cdots O), which can further stabilize

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the guest in the complex. These carbon-oxygen hydrogen bonding are well reputed in the literature.^[6]

Another feature in this cleft is the presence of the two phenol groups in positions C-3 and C-7, since they form intramolecular H-bonds which fix the carboxamide and sulfonamide conformations. This makes the cleft more rigid^[7] and might improve catalysis since the negative charge on the carbonyl oxygen in the transition state would attract the carboxamide hydrogen, leaving therefore, a negative carboxamide carbonyl group which also strengthens the phenolic H-bond. The same reasoning may be valid for the sulfonamide sulfuranyl group; thus, the four H-bonds in the complex (the two intramolecular and the two intermolecular with the guest) might be stronger in the transition state and a larger reduction of the transition state energy could be achieved.

Also, the presence of the two phenolic groups in the naphthalene skeleton showed a further benefit since they direct sulfonation in the 2-naphthoic acid to position C-8; therefore, chlorosulfonation of the commercially available 3,7-dihydroxy-2-naphthoic acid leads to the desired skeleton, as shown in Scheme 1.

i. $\text{ClSO}_2\text{H}/\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$; ii. bis(trifluoromethyl)aniline; iii. *p*-dimethylaminoaniline/DCC.

Scheme 1. Structure and preparation of receptor **3**.

To improve the binding properties of the cleft, a bis(trifluoromethyl)aniline was chosen as the sulfonamide substituent, since this group is known to increase the H-bonds strength.^[8] The carboxamide was substituted with a *p*-dimethylamino aniline group. This electron-rich aromatic ring may provide additional stabilization of the complex due to charge transfer interactions with electron-deficient aromatic rings (Scheme 1).

Receptor **3** crystallizes well from methanol, yielding beautiful yellow crystals suitable for X-ray analysis (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Crystal structure of the complex between receptor **3** and methanol. Selected distances between heavy atoms [Å]: intramolecular H-bonds: 2.592(4) and 2.548(4); width oxyanion hole NH-NH: 4.727(4); intermolecular H-bonds with methanol: 2.830(4) and 2.873(4).

The X-ray structure of receptor **3** was highly promising, showing the expected conformation for the sulfonamide, which is fixed with

a short intramolecular H-bond (2.592 Å) same as for carboxamide (2.548 Å). The size of the oxyanion-hole, measured as the distance between the two nitrogen atoms is below 5 Å (4.727 Å), quite close to the average oxyanion-hole distance found in many enzymes.^[9] The X-ray structure shows a methanol molecule located inside the cleft, accepting two strong H-bonds from the receptor NHs, with 2.830 Å (sulfonamide NH) and 2.873 Å (carboxamide NH). This methanol molecule forms a third H-bond in the crystal (2.782 Å), acting as an H-bond donor with the carboxamide carbonyl group of a second molecule of receptor **3**. This provides an ideal surrounding for the methanol forming three strong H-bonds (Figure S29). Another remarkable feature of this structure is the large torsion angle that forms the *p*-dimethylamino aniline with the carboxamide carbonyl group (67°). This sacrifices a great amount of conjugation energy, but seems to be outweighed by the π - π stacking interaction between the dimethylamino aniline ring and the bis(trifluoromethyl)aniline of another molecule of receptor **3** (Figures S30-S31).

NMR titration experiments with this receptor evidenced a weak binding: firstly, compound **3** is only sparingly soluble in chloroform and, secondly it dimerizes in this solvent. Although dimerization studies showed a small constant of 15 M⁻¹, it was enough to discourage association of electron-deficient aromatic guests as methyl 3,5-dinitrobenzoate, 3,5-dinitrobenzyl alcohol or 3,5-dinitrobenzamide. In no case, significant shifts for the receptor **3** protons were observed upon addition of up to 6 equivalents of the corresponding guests. Modelling studies suggest for the dimer a structure stabilized by up to 4 intermolecular H-bonds, with one of the sulfonamide oxygens of one receptor setting 2 strong hydrogen bonds with the NHs of another molecule of receptor (Table S4).

Trying to improve the properties of this cleft, a larger aromatic sheet of 1-naphthylamine was included as the sulfonamide substituent. The steric bulk of the naphthylamine yielded a conformational rigid compound, since the *peri* CH proton has to be located between the nitrogen and the oxygen atoms of the sulfonamide. On the other hand and to increase the number of hydrogen bonds, the widely used 2-amino-6-methylpyridine explored by Hamilton^[3] and Diederich,^[10] was installed as by an amide linkage in the carboxamide, yielding receptor **6**. The

i. $\text{ClSO}_2\text{H}/\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$; ii. α -naphthylamine; iii. 2-amino-6-methylpyridine / BuLi.

Scheme 2. Structure and preparation of receptor **6**.

While the reaction of the sulfonyl chloride **4** with 1-naphthylamine was straightforward, the introduction of the aminopyridine was quite challenging. It was not possible to prepare the acid chloride, either with oxalyl chloride, thionyl chloride or phosphorus pentachloride. Coupling the acid and the aminopyridine with HBTU or DCC also failed to produce the desired amide. Finally, it was possible to obtain the desired compound **6** by reacting the

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methyl ester **5** with a large excess of the aminopyridine anion in THF at room temperature.

Receptor **6** crystallizes from a methanol/acetic acid mixture (99/1) yielding suitable crystals for X-ray analysis. Surprisingly, the structure does not correspond to the expected acetic acid complex, but rather to receptor **6** with a methanol molecule in the cleft (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Crystal structure of the complex between receptor **6** and methanol. Selected distances between heavy atoms [Å]: intramolecular H-bonds: 2.591(2) and 2.688(2); width oxanion hole NH_{sulfonamide}-CO_{carboxamide}: 4.510(2); intermolecular H-bonds with methanol: 2.902(2) and 2.683(2).

As expected, the naphthylamine *peri* CH proton is located between the sulfonamide nitrogen and oxygen atoms, yielding a nitrogen atom with an almost completely loss of conjugation with the aromatic ring (torsion angle 86°, Figure S32). On the other side, the aminopyridine is almost coplanar with the naphthalene backbone, with almost no loss of conjugation energy. Stacking in this complex is dominated by naphthalene pile up (Figure S33). The most striking feature is the H-bond pattern of the methanol molecule in the cleft. In this case, the methanol acts both as an H-bond acceptor with the sulfonamide NH (2.902 Å) and as a donor with the carboxamide carbonyl group (2.684 Å). This leaves a narrow cleft of only 4.510 Å, in which the carboxamide is twisted 180° respect to its previous position in receptor **3**. Therefore, the intramolecular H-bond with the phenol at C-3 is now set with the amide NH as a donor. Since the phenolic oxygen is not a good H-bond acceptor, this H-bond is long for an intramolecular one (2.688 Å). This phenol group also acts as a donor, setting a H-bond with another methanol molecules with acts as the acceptor (2.757 Å, Figure S34). In this way, methanol forms again the three possible H-bonds.

Pleasingly, crystallization of receptor **6** from pure glacial acetic acid leaves the expected acetic acid associate (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Crystal structure of the complex between receptor **6** and acetic acid. Selected distances between heavy atoms [Å]: intramolecular H-bonds: 2.562(3) and 2.588(2); width oxanion hole NH-NH: 5.076(2); intermolecular H-bonds with acetic acid: NH_{sulfonamide} 2.821(2); NH_{carboxamide} 2.897(2); N_{pyridine} 2.662(2).

X-ray analysis shows a cleft between the sulfonamide and carboxamide NHs larger than in receptor **3**, with 5.076 Å compared to the previous 4.727 Å for compound **3**. This is expected, since the acetic acid carbonyl forms weaker and larger H-bonds than the methanol oxygen. The differences in H-bond distances for sulfonamide and carboxamide NHs also corroborate that the cleft can adapt to the strength of the different H-bonds (Figures 2 and 4). The shortest H-bond corresponds, nevertheless, to the carboxyl proton and the basic pyridine nitrogen, with a distance of 2.662 Å. Interestingly, two more acetic acid molecules show up in this crystalline structure (Figure S35), with H-bonds between the oxygen atoms (2.658 Å and 2.642 Å) similar to the already reported for acetic acid dimers.^[11]

To study the stability of the acetic acid complex, an NMR titration was carried out. Adding acetic acid to a $1.5 \cdot 10^{-3} M$ solution of receptor **6** in deuteriochloroform induces large shifts in the receptor **6** signals; in particular, H-1 shifts from 9.126 ppm to 9.329 ppm showing its proximity with the acetic acid carboxyl in the complex. Deshielding of the pyridine protons also confirms the formation of the strong H-bond between the acid and the pyridine nitrogen. An association constant of $6.7 \cdot 10^3 M^{-1}$ was determined, which is a good result compared to single amidopyridine complexes in the range of hundreds. The geometry of the complex in solution seems to be similar to the one in the crystalline state, in which the acetic acid is over the naphthylamine ring; the shielding cone of this aromatic ring should produce an acetic acid methyl group absorbing upfield compared to the free acid. Indeed, a chemical shift of 1.6 ppm was estimated for this methyl group in the complex (Figure S21).

However, and despite the large aromatic sheet of receptor **6**, no charge transfer was achieved with electron-deficient aromatic compound as dinitro or trinitrobenzoic acids.

With the aim of combining H-bonds with charge-transfer effects in the associate, a new receptor was designed. The previous disappointing results obtained with the dimethylamino aniline fragment in receptor **3** suggested to include in the receptor a more flexible electron-rich aromatic unit for charge-transfer and a dimethylamino benzylamine fragment was chosen; rotation over the methylene bond might adjust the geometry while maximizing charge-transfer effects with suitable guests.

Scheme 3. Structure and preparation of receptor **8**.

Scheme 3. Structure and preparation of receptor **8**.

Receptor **8** is highly soluble in chloroform and initial qualitative experiments show the development of deep colours upon addition of electron-poor guests as 3,5-dinitrobenzoic or 2,4,6-trinitrobenzoic acids.

¹H NMR shifts of receptor **8** in chloroform strongly depends on the concentration, suggesting the presence of a dimer; dilution experiments changing receptor concentration from $6.32 \cdot 10^{-2} M$ to $1.23 \cdot 10^{-4} M$ afforded a self-association constant of $44 M^{-1}$

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(Figure S22). Despite dimer formation, receptor **8** is a good receptor for electron-deficient guests. As shown in Figure 5, the modelling study presents a good fit for the planar 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid and the receptor **8**, in which the electron-poor aromatic ring is nicely on top of the dimethylaniline fragment while three linear H-bonds are set.

Figure 5. Modelling studies. Associate between receptor **8** and 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid, showing H-bonds and π - π interactions.

^1H NMR titration with 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid at constant concentration of the receptor ($2.47 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{M}$) was performed and the shielding of the signals of the dimethylaniline aromatic protons evidenced the proximity of the dinitrobenzoyl aromatic group. On the other hand, all the pyridine signals were deshielded, as expected for the formation of strong H-bonds. An association constant of $K_a = 3.4 \cdot 10^4 \text{M}^{-1}$ was determined (Figures S23-S24). ^1H NMR bidimensional spectra allow the assignment of all the signals and ROESY, in particular, confirms the structure of the proposed associate with cross correlations among the dinitrobenzoyl and the dimethylaniline protons (Figure S13). To assess the effect of the charge transfer, a titration with benzoic acid was carried out. Under similar conditions (constant concentration of receptor **8** of $3.3 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{M}$) addition of benzoic acid developed no colour and an association constant of $6.3 \cdot 10^2 \text{M}^{-1}$ was determined. Since 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid ($pK_a = 2.82$) is stronger than benzoic acid ($pK_a = 4.21$),^[12] the decrease in association constant might also be attributed partially to this fact; but also, the small association constant with benzoic acid could also be explained because sulfonamido pyridines show a worse behaviour than the corresponding carboxamido pyridines.^[13]

While the planar dinitrobenzoic acid fits well in this cleft, the association of 2,4,6-trinitrobenzoic acid is not so obvious since its geometry is completely different. An X-ray study with diamino pyridine^[14] shows the carboxylic acid forming an 80° angle with the aromatic ring. Nevertheless, the charge transfer effect also takes place with this host, probably because the benzylamine can rotate the methylene bond to get a reasonable overlap. A modelling study, showing this possibility is shown in the Figure 6.

Figure 6. Modelling studies. Associate between receptor **8** and 2,4,6-trinitrobenzoic acid, showing H-bonds and π - π interactions.

Titration in chloroform solution yielded a high association constant $K_a = 8.1 \cdot 10^4 \text{M}^{-1}$. As in the case of dinitrobenzoic acid, all the

signals of the complex could be assigned to the corresponding protons through bidimensional spectra.

The good results obtained with receptor **8** and nitrobenzoic acids encouraged us to test non-acid nitroaromatic compounds, hoping that the combination of the hydrogen bonds and charge transfer may allow significant association.

First attempt with methyl 3,5-dinitrobenzoate showed a low association constant. It develops a weak charge transfer band with very small shifts in the ^1H NMR signals. Plot of the signals yielded straight lines and therefore a conventional titration may provide very large errors. As shown in the X-ray studies, alcohols are better H-bond acceptors than esters and, indeed, dinitrobenzyl alcohol yields an increased colour in the complex and the association constant could be determined, $K_a = 23 \text{M}^{-1}$. Finally, 3,5-dinitrobenzamide was also tested. This guest can form three H-bonds and therefore is better than the ester and the alcohol, yielding a $K_a = 298 \text{M}^{-1}$. In both cases the expected deshielding of the NHs and the pyridine signals can be observed so as the shielding of the dimethylaniline protons due to the proximity of the dinitrobenzoyl aromatic ring.

Table 1. Binding constants determined from NMR titrations in CDCl_3 at 20°C .

Entry	Receptor	Guest	$\log K_a$
1	3	[a]	1.18
2	6	Acetic acid	3.83 ± 0.03
3	8	[a]	1.64
4	8	3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid	4.53 ± 0.14
5	8	Benzoic acid	2.79 ± 0.02
6	8	2,4,6-trinitrobenzoic acid	4.91 ± 0.40
7	8	3,5-dinitrobenzyl alcohol	1.36 ± 0.02
8	8	3,5-dinitrobenzamide	2.47 ± 0.01

[a] Self-association constants through dilution experiments.

In summary, placing a sulfonamide on the C-8 position of a 2-naphthamide affords an adjustable oxyanion hole which can adapt to carbonyl or alcohol oxygens as shown in X-ray studies. These X-ray studies show two possible geometries for the complex with methanol, one in which the receptor acts donating two H-bonds to the methanol molecule and another in which methanol also acts as the H-bond donor. The combination with aminopyridines allow good association with carboxylic acids, while combination with electron-rich aromatics, provide large association with electron-deficient aromatic acids or even association with non-acidic dinitroaromatic guests.

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Keywords: oxyanion hole • molecular recognition • hydrogen bonds • charge transfer • carboxylic acids

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Torsion angle around the sulfonamide bond gives these oxyanion hole-like receptors a variable size cleft. As stronger H-bonds imply shorter distances between H-bond donors and acceptors, these clefts with sulfonamide and carboxamide functions might be of interest in catalysis. X-ray crystal structures confirm the formation of two strong linear H-bonds between the NHs and carbonyl or alcohol oxygens, showing the adaptability of the cleft.

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